

The Beta Kumaraswamy Lindley distribution: Properties and Application

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Abstract: In this paper, a characterization of Lindley distribution is proposed through the beta generated Kumaraswamy-G family of distribution and is named as the beta Kumaraswamy Lindley distribution. Some statistical properties of the proposed distribution including its moments, skewness, kurtosis, order statistics, hazard-rate function, reliability function, Bonferroni and Lorenz curve are discussed. The parameters of the proposed distribution are obtained by using the maximum likelihood estimation method and the applicability of the proposed model is shown using the two real life data sets.

Keywords - Beta-G class, Kumaraswamy Lindley distribution, moments, order statistics, hazard rate function, reliability function.

I. INTRODUCTION

The scope of the lifetime distributions is quite huge and they are generally used to study real life problems, mainly in applied fields like in medical, banking, engineering and in others. Among all the lifetime distributions, Weibull and Lindley distribution play very important roles in the statistical literature. Lindley [10] proposed the popular Lindley distribution. Hereafter, many authors developed several lifetime models based on Lindley probability model; Eugene et al. [6] proposed beta-normal distribution and showed its applications, [9] developed by Kumaraswamy, Zakerzadah et al. [20] proposed generalized Lindley distribution, Nadarajah et al. [15] developed a generalized Lindley distribution, Bashiru [2] discussed new exponentiated extended inverse exponential distribution, Nadarajah et al. [14] proposed the beta Gumbel distribution, Cordeiro et al. [4] developed Kumaraswamy Gumbel distribution, Maurya et al. [12] proposed an extended Lindley distribution. In recent years, several generalization techniques have been developed by using Lindley and Kumaraswamy distribution because of their flexibility and increasing nature of hazard rate function. Almost in all the above mentioned generalized models, one common thing is that they introduced some additional parameters to increase the flexibility of its baseline distribution.

Till date, a no. of new class of family of distributions have been developed. One of them is Kumaraswamy-G distribution (kw-G) . Cordeiro et al. [3] proposed a new family of generalized distribution, by combining two other distributions for constructing a new family of Kumaraswamy generalized(Kw-G) distribution and derived some special cases and statistical properties. Nadarajah et al. [17] developed general results for the Kumaraswamy-G distribution and explored some of its mathematical properties and obtained the Maximum Likelihood estimators of its parameters .

Handique et a. [7] proposed the Beta Generated Kumaraswamy-G family of distribution and explored some of its mathematical properties. Madaki et al. [11] proposed Beta Kumaraswamy Burr type X distribution. Zakeia et al. [21] introduced characterization of the Beta Kumaraswamy Exponential distribution and derived some of its mathematical properties. Till now, not much work has been done towards developing the special case of Beta generated Kumaraswamy-G family of distributions with the one parameter Lindley as the baseline distribution. Hence, in this paper, an attempt has been made to develop and study a special case of BKw-G distribution by taking Lindley as the baseline distribution.

The family of the Kumaraswamy-H distributions(Kw-H), has the cdf

$$G(x) = 1 - \{1 - [H(x)]^a\}^b \quad (1)$$

where $a, b > 0$ are the shape parameters and $H(x)$ is the c.d.f of the continuous baseline distribution. Considering the one parameter Lindley distribution as the baseline distribution, the cdf of the Kumaraswamy Lindley(Kw-L) distribution is obtained as shown below

$$G(x) = 1 - [1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^a]^b \quad (2)$$

Here a, b are the shape parameters and θ is the scale parameter. Furthermore, Eugene et al. [6] proposed a Beta-G class of generalized distributions whose cdf is

$$F(x) = \frac{1}{B(l,m)} \int_0^{G(x)} w^{l-1} (1-w)^{m-1} dw \quad (3)$$

where $l, m > 0$ are the shape parameters.

In this research work, a new probability distribution is developed by taking the Kw-L distribution as the baseline distribution of the beta-G class of generalized distribution which is named as the beta Kumaraswamy Lindley (BKw-L) distribution. The later part of this paper is organized as follows: section 2 presents the derivation of the pdf and cdf of the BKw-L distribution. Statistical properties are inspected in section 3. Section 4 presents the expressions of the reliability and hazard curves of the proposed distribution. Section 5 shows the distribution of order statistics. Simulation and estimation of parameters are attempted in section 6 &7 respectively. Section 8 shows the applicability of the proposed distribution with two real life data sets and section 9 contains the concluding remarks.

II. DERIVATION OF THE BKW-L DISTRIBUTION

In this section, we derive the density function of the five parameter beta Kumaraswamy Lindley (BKw-L) distribution.

By substituting (2), as the baseline distribution in (3), the c.d.f of BKw-L is obtained as follows :

$$F(x) = \frac{1}{B(l,m)} \int_0^{1 - [1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^a]^b} w^{l-1} (1-w)^{m-1} dw; x > 0, a, b, l, m, \theta > 0 \quad (4)$$

The c.d.f is in the form of an incomplete beta distribution and the corresponding probability density function is obtained by

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &= \frac{d}{dx} F(x) \\ &= \frac{d}{dx} \left\{ \frac{1}{B(l,m)} \int_0^{1 - [1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^a]^b} w^{l-1} (1-w)^{m-1} dw \right\}; x > 0, a, b, l, m > 0 \end{aligned}$$

After simplifications, the p.d.f of BKw-L distribution is obtained as

$$f(x) = \frac{ab\theta^2}{B(l,m)(1+\theta)} e^{-\theta x} (1+x) [1 - \{1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^a\}^b]^{l-1}$$

$$x [1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^a]^{mb-1} \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^{a-1}; x > 0, a, b, l, m, \theta > 0 \quad (5)$$

where, a is the scale parameter, b, l and m are the shape parameters and θ is a location parameter.

Figure 1 and 2 display respectively the p.d.f and c.d.f of BKw-L distribution for different parameter values

Fig. 1: p.d.f plots of BKw-L distribution for different combination of parameter values

Fig. 2: c.d.f plots of BKw-L distribution for different combination of parameter values

III. STATISTICAL PROPERTIES

A. Moments and some related statistical measures :

The r^{th} moment about origin of the BKw-L distribution is given by

$$\mu_r' = E(x^r) = \frac{ab\theta^2}{B(l,m)(1+\theta)} \int_0^\infty x^r e^{-\theta x} x [1 - \{1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^a\}^b]^{l-1} x [1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^a]^{mb-1} \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^{a-1} dx$$

$$\left[\int_0^{\infty} x^{r+1} e^{-\theta x} [1 - \{1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^a\}^b]^{l-1} \right. \\ \left. [1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^a]^{mb-1} \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^{a-1} dx \right]; x > 0, a, b, l, m > 0 \quad (6)$$

Using this r^{th} order moment, the central moments, coefficients of skewness (β_1) and kurtosis (β_2) can be obtained. The moments have been evaluated using suitable numerical techniques [18] due to unavailability of a closed form solution.

B. Median:

The median of the BKw-L distribution can be found by solving the following equation :

$$\frac{1}{B(l,m)} \int_0^{1-[1-\{1-(1+\frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^a]^b} w^{l-1}(1-w)^{m-1} dw = \frac{1}{2} \quad (7)$$

C. Mode:

The mode of the BKw-L distribution can be found by solving the following equation

$$\frac{d}{dx} f(x) = 0$$

Upon simplifying the equation we get,

$$\Rightarrow c e^{-\theta x} [1 - \{1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^a\}^b]^{l-1} \mathbf{x} \\ [1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^a]^{mb-1} \mathbf{x} \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^{a-1} \mathbf{x} \\ [\{1 - \theta(x+1)\} + \{ab(l-1)\theta e^{-\theta x}(1+x)\} \mathbf{x} [1 - \{1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^a\}^b]^{-1} \\ [1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^a]^{b-1} \\ \mathbf{x} \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^{a-1} \{\frac{\theta(1+x)}{(1+\theta)}\} + \{ab\theta(mb-1)e^{-\theta x}(1+x) \\ (1 - (1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x})^a)^{-1} \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^{a-1} \{\frac{\theta(1+x)}{(1+\theta)}\} + \\ \{\theta(a-1)e^{-\theta x}(1+x) \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^{-1} \{\frac{\theta(1+x)}{(1+\theta)}\}\}] = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$\text{where } c = \frac{ab\theta^2}{B(l,m)(1+\theta)}$$

Table 1 shows the values of mean, variance, median, mode, skewness and kurtosis for the different values of the parameters

Table 1: Mean,variance,median,mode,skewness and kurtosis for the different values of the parameters

Increasing the value of a and keeping the other parameter fixed										
a	b	θ	l	m	Mean	Variance	Median	Mode	Skewness	Kurtosis
1.5	1.2	0.8	3	2.5	2.1133	0.7446	2.0025	2.2732	0.6387	4.0212
2	1.2	0.8	3	2.5	2.5082	0.7855	2.4056	2.6441	0.5259	3.8810
2.5	1.2	0.8	3	2.5	2.8225	0.8076	0.8076	2.9402	0.4668	3.8098

Increasing the value of b and keeping the other parameter fixed										
a	b	θ	l	m	Mean	Variance	Median	Mode	Skewness	Kurtosis
1.5	2	0.8	3	2.5	1.4960	0.3539	1.4253	2.2601	0.5339	3.8232
1.5	3	0.8	3	2.5	1.4361	0.2012	1.0930	2.3456	0.4753	3.7059
1.5	4	0.8	3	2.5	0.9470	0.1362	0.9066	2.4726	0.4447	3.6422

Increasing the value of θ and keeping the other parameter fixed										
a	b	θ	l	m	Mean	Variance	Median	Mode	Skewness	Kurtosis
1.5	4	0.8	3	2.5	0.9474	0.5082	0.9066	2.4726	7.9786	8.0121
1.5	4	1.2	3	2.5	0.5637	0.0531	0.5357	1.5353	0.5339	3.7791
1.5	4	1.8	3	2.5	0.3366	0.0203	0.3182	0.9473	0.6203	3.9225

Increasing the value of l and keeping the other parameter fixed										
a	b	θ	l	m	Mean	Variance	Median	Mode	Skewness	Kurtosis
1.5	4	0.8	3	2.5	0.9474	0.1362	0.9066	2.4726	0.4447	3.6422
1.5	4	0.8	4	2.5	1.0761	0.1359	1.0386	2.4963	0.3840	3.5913
1.5	4	0.8	5	2.5	1.1792	0.1346	1.1438	2.5192	0.3515	3.5679

Increasing the value of m and keeping the other parameter fixed										
a	b	θ	l	m	Mean	Variance	Median	Mode	Skewness	Kurtosis
1.5	4	0.8	3	2.5	0.9470	0.1362	0.9066	2.4726	0.4447	3.6422
1.5	4	0.8	3	3	0.8604	0.1106	0.8249	2.2832	0.4113	3.5722
1.5	4	0.8	3	4	0.7367	0.0795	0.7078	2.0369	0.3727	3.4892

The following remarks can be made based on Table 1:

- 1) By increasing a , the mean, variance, median and mode increase, but the skewness and kurtosis decrease.
- 2) By increasing b , only the mode increases. On the other hand, the skewness increases as the value of b decreases.
- 3) By increasing the location parameter θ , the values of mean, variance, median, mode, skewness and kurtosis decrease.
- 4) Simultaneously, by increasing l , the values of mean, median and mode increase, although variance, skewness and kurtosis decrease.
- 5) As we increase the value of m , it gives the same result as the location parameter θ .

D. Some additional properties:

i. RATIO OF TWO INDEPENDENTLY DISTRIBUTED BKw-L RANDOM VARIABLES:

Let X and Y be two independently distributed random variables which follow BKw-L probability law with parameters $(a_1, b_1, l_1, m_1, \theta_1)$ and BKw-L $(a_2, b_2, l_2, m_2, \theta_2)$ respectively. Then the distribution of X/Y is obtained as shown below:

Let us take $X/Y = v$ and $X = u$ then $Y = u/v$ and $X = u$

The Jacobian of transformation is given by

$$J = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{\partial x}{\partial u} & \frac{\partial y}{\partial u} \\ \frac{\partial x}{\partial v} & \frac{\partial y}{\partial v} \end{vmatrix} = \frac{u}{v^2}$$

After simplification, the pdf of V can be written as-

$$g_1(v) = c_1 c_2 \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\theta_1 u} e^{-\theta_2 (u/v)} (1 + (u/v)) \frac{u}{v^2} \\ \times [1 - \{1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta_1 u}{1+\theta_1}) e^{-\theta_1 u}\}^{a_1}\}^{b_1}]^{l_1-1} \\ \times [1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta_1 u}{1+\theta_1}) e^{-\theta_1 u}\}^{a_1}]^{m_1 b_1-1} \\ \times \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta_1 u}{1+\theta_1}) e^{-\theta_1 u}\}^{a_1-1} \\ \times [1 - \{1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta_2 u}{1+\theta_2}) e^{-\theta_2 u}\}^{a_2}\}^{b_2}]^{l_2-1} \\ \times [1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta_2 u}{1+\theta_2}) e^{-\theta_2 u}\}^{a_2}]^{m_2 b_2-1} \\ \times \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta_2 u}{1+\theta_2}) e^{-\theta_2 u}\}^{a_2-1} du$$

where

$$c_1 = \frac{a_1 b_1 \theta_1^2}{B(l_1, m_1)(1+\theta_1)} \text{ and } c_2 = \frac{a_2 b_2 \theta_2^2}{B(l_2, m_2)(1+\theta_2)}$$

Figure 3 shows the plots of the ratio of two independently distributed random variables

Fig. 3: Plots of the ratio of two independently distributed BKw-L random variables

i. Product of two independently distributed BKw-L random variables

Let X and Y be two independent random variables which follow BKw-L distribution with parameters $(a_1, b_1, l_1, m_1, \theta_1)$ and BKw-L $(a_2, b_2, l_2, m_2, \theta_2)$ respectively. Then the distribution of XY is obtained as shown below.

Let us take $XY = u, Y = v$ then $X = u/v$ and $Y = v$

Now the Jacobian of transformation is given by-

$$J = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{\partial x}{\partial u} & \frac{\partial y}{\partial u} \\ \frac{\partial x}{\partial v} & \frac{\partial y}{\partial v} \end{vmatrix} = \frac{1}{v}$$

After simplification the pdf of U can be written as –

$$g_1(u) = c_1 c_2 \int_0^\infty e^{-\theta_1(u/v)} e^{-\theta_2 v} (1 + (u/v)) \frac{1}{v} \mathbf{x} [1 - \{1 - \{1 - \frac{\theta_1 u}{1+\theta_1}\} e^{-\theta_1 \frac{u}{v}}\}^{a_1}\}^{b_1}]^{l_1-1} \\ \mathbf{x} [1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta_1 u}{1+\theta_1}) e^{-\theta_1 \frac{u}{v}}\}^{a_1}]^{m_1 b_1 - 1} \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta_1 u}{1+\theta_1}) e^{-\theta_1 \frac{u}{v}}\}^{a_1 - 1} \\ \mathbf{x} [1 - \{1 - \{1 - \frac{\theta_2 v}{1+\theta_2}\} e^{-\theta_2 v}\}^{a_2}\}^{b_2}]^{l_2-1} [1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta_2 v}{1+\theta_2}) e^{-\theta_2 v}\}^{a_2}]^{m_2 b_2 - 1} \mathbf{x} \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta_2 v}{1+\theta_2}) e^{-\theta_2 v}\}^{a_2 - 1} dv$$

where

$$c_1 = \frac{a_1 b_1 \theta_1^2}{B(l_1, m_1)(1+\theta_1)} \text{ and } c_2 = \frac{a_2 b_2 \theta_2^2}{B(l_2, m_2)(1+\theta_2)}$$

Figure 4 shows the plots of the product of two independently distributed random variables

Fig. 4: Plots of the product of two independently distributed BKw-L random variables

IV. RELIABILITY PROPERTIES

A. Hazard Rate function:

The hazard rate function is the instant rate of failure at a given time t, while the reliability function is the probability of the non-failure occurring before time t.

The hazard function of the BKw-L distribution is given by

$$h(x) = \frac{f(x)}{1 - F(x)}, x > 0, a, b, l, m, \theta > 0$$

$$h(x) = \frac{\frac{ab\theta^2}{B(l,m)(1+\theta)} e^{-\theta x(1+x)} [1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta}) e^{-\theta x}\} a]^b l^{-1} [1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta}) e^{-\theta x}\} a]^{mb-1} [1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta}) e^{-\theta x}]^{a-1}}{1 - [\frac{1}{B(l,m)} \int_0^{1 - (1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta}) e^{-\theta x})^a} w^{l-1} (1-w)^{m-1} dw]} \tag{9}$$

The plot of hazard rate function of the BKw-L distribution for different values of the parameters is displayed in figure 5:

Fig. 5: The hazard rate function plots of the BKw-L distribution for different parameter values.

From Figure 5, it is clear that the hazard rate function curve increases with time when the value of θ decreases, on the other hand when the value of a , and b decrease while increasing the value of θ , the curves remain approximately constant over time.

A. Reliability function:

The reliability function of the BKw-L distribution is given by

$$R(x) = 1 - F(x); \quad x > 0, a, b, \theta, l, m > 0$$

$$= 1 - \left[\frac{1}{B(l,m)} \int_0^{1 - \left(1 - \left(1 + \frac{\theta x}{1 + \theta}\right)^a e^{-\theta x}\right)^b} w^{l-1} (1-w)^{m-1} dw \right] (10)$$

The shape of the corresponding reliability function of the BKw-L distribution for different values of the parameters has been found in Figure 6.

Fig. 6: The reliability function plots of the BKw-L distribution for different combination of the values of parameters

V. ORDER STATISTICS

Let $x_{(1)} \leq x_{(2)} \leq x_{(3)} \leq \dots \leq x_{(n)}$ denote the order statistic of a random sample x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n from the BKw-L distribution (a, b, l, m, θ) with cdf $F(x)$ and pdf $f(x)$. Then the pdf of $x_{(r)}$ can be written as

$$f_r(x_{(r)}) = \frac{n!}{(r-1)!(n-r)!} f(x)[F(x)]^{r-1}[1 - F(x)]^{n-r} \tag{11}$$

The pdf of the largest order statistic $x_{(n)}$ has been obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} f_{x_{(n)}}(x) &= n\{F(x)\}^{n-1}f(x) \\ &= n\left\{\frac{1}{B(l,m)} \int_0^{1-\{1-\{1-(1+\frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^a\}^b} w^{l-1}(1-w)^{m-1}\right\}^{n-1} x \\ &\quad \frac{ab\theta^2}{B(l,m)(1+\theta)} e^{-\theta x}(1+x)[1 - \{1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^a\}^b]^{l-1} x \\ &\quad [1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^a]^{mb-1} \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^{a-1} \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

The probability curve of the largest order statistic for the different sets of parameters is shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7: Probability density function curve of the largest order statistic of BKw-L distribution for different parameter values

The pdf of the smallest order statistic $x_{(1)}$ has been obtained as

Fig. 8: Probability density function curve of the smallest order statistic of BKw-L for different parameter values

VI. LORENZ AND BONFERRONI CURVES:

Lorenz and Bonferroni curves are the most widely used inequality measures in income and wealth distribution and given by Dagum [5]. These two curves mainly depend on the following length-biased distribution with pdf $f^*(x)$ given by

$$f^*(x) = \frac{xf(x)}{E(x)} \tag{14}$$

where $f(x)$ is the pdf of the base distribution with mean $E(x)$.

Accordingly, Lorenz and Bonferroni curves denoted by $L(x)$ and $B(x)$ respectively, are defined by –

$$L(x) = \frac{F^*(x)}{E(x)} \tag{15}$$

$$\text{and } B(x) = \frac{L(x)}{F(x)} \tag{16}$$

Where $F^*(x)$ is the cdf of the length-biased distribution.

After simplification the following expressions for $L(x)$ and $B(x)$ are obtained:

$$f^*(x) = \frac{x \frac{ab\theta^2}{B(l,m)(1+\theta)} e^{-\theta x(1+x)} [1-\{1-\{1-(1+\frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}a\}b]^{l-1} [1-\{1-(1+\frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}a]^{mb-1} \{1-(1+\frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^{a-1}}{\frac{ab\theta^2}{B(l,m)(1+\theta)} \int_0^\infty x e^{-\theta x(1+x)} [1-\{1-\{1-(1+\frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}a\}b]^{l-1} [1-\{1-(1+\frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}a]^{mb-1} \{1-(1+\frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^{a-1} dx} \tag{17}$$

$$L(x) = \frac{\int_0^x f^*(x) dx}{\frac{ab\theta^2}{B(l,m)(1+\theta)} \int_0^\infty x e^{-\theta x(1+x)} [1-\{1-\{1-(1+\frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}a\}b]^{l-1} [1-\{1-(1+\frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}a]^{mb-1} \{1-(1+\frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^{a-1} dx} \tag{18}$$

$$B(x) = \frac{\frac{ab\theta^2}{B(l,m)(1+\theta)} \int_0^\infty x e^{-\theta x(1+x)} [1-\{1-\{1-(1+\frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}a\}b]^{l-1} [1-\{1-(1+\frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}a]^{mb-1} \{1-(1+\frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}^{a-1} dx}{\frac{1}{B(l,m)} \int_0^{1-\{1-\{1-(1+\frac{\theta x}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x}\}a\}b} w^{l-1} (1-w)^{m-1} dw} \tag{19}$$

Figure 9 and 10 display respectively the Lorenz and Bonferroni curves

Figure 9: The Lorenz plot of the BKw-L distribution for a specific set of values of the parameters

Figure 10: The Bonferroni plot of the BKw-L distribution for a specific set of values of the parameters

VII. ESTIMATION OF PARAMETERS

This part comprises the estimation of the unknown parameters of the proposed model by using the maximum likelihood estimation method.

A. Maximum Likelihood Method of Estimation:

Let x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n be a random sample of size n from the proposed distribution. Then the likelihood function is obtained as

$$\begin{aligned}
 L &= \prod_{i=1}^n f(x_i; \theta) \\
 &= \left\{ \frac{ab\theta^2}{B(l,m)(1+\theta)} \right\}^n e^{-\theta \sum_{i=1}^n x_i} \prod_{i=1}^n (1+x_i)^{-x} \prod_{i=1}^n [1 - \{1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x_i}\}^a\}^b]^{l-1-x} \\
 &\quad \prod_{i=1}^n [1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x_i}\}^a]^{mb-1} \prod_{i=1}^n \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1+\theta})e^{-\theta x_i}\}^{a-1}
 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

After taking logarithm on both sides of equation (20), we get the log-likelihood function as

$$\begin{aligned} \ln L &= n * \log \left\{ \frac{ab\theta^2}{B(l,m)(1+\theta)} \right\} - \theta \sum_{i=1}^n x_i + \sum_{i=1}^n \log(1+x_i) + \\ &(l-1) \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\log \left[1 - \left\{ 1 - \left\{ 1 - \left(1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1+\theta} \right) e^{-\theta x_i} \right\}^a \right\}^b \right] \right] + (mb-1) \\ &\sum_{i=1}^n \log \left[1 - \left\{ 1 - \left(1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1+\theta} \right) e^{-\theta x_i} \right\}^a \right] + (a-1) \sum_{i=1}^n \log \left[\left\{ 1 - \left(1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1+\theta} \right) e^{-\theta x_i} \right\} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Now, the parameters are obtained by solving the following maximum likelihood equations

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \ln L &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left\{ n * \log \left\{ \frac{ab\theta^2}{B(l,m)(1+\theta)} \right\} - \theta \sum_{i=1}^n x_i + \sum_{i=1}^n \log(1+x_i) + \right. \\ &(l-1) \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\log \left[1 - \left\{ 1 - \left\{ 1 - \left(1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1+\theta} \right) e^{-\theta x_i} \right\}^a \right\}^b \right] \right] + (mb-1) \\ &\left. \sum_{i=1}^n \log \left[1 - \left\{ 1 - \left(1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1+\theta} \right) e^{-\theta x_i} \right\}^a \right] + (a-1) \sum_{i=1}^n \log \left[\left\{ 1 - \left(1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1+\theta} \right) e^{-\theta x_i} \right\} \right] \right\} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial a} \ln L &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial a} \left\{ n * \log \left\{ \frac{ab\theta^2}{B(l,m)(1+\theta)} \right\} - \theta \sum_{i=1}^n x_i + \sum_{i=1}^n \log(1+x_i) + \right. \\ &(l-1) \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\log \left[1 - \left\{ 1 - \left\{ 1 - \left(1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1+\theta} \right) e^{-\theta x_i} \right\}^a \right\}^b \right] \right] + (mb-1) \\ &\left. \sum_{i=1}^n \log \left[1 - \left\{ 1 - \left(1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1+\theta} \right) e^{-\theta x_i} \right\}^a \right] + (a-1) \sum_{i=1}^n \log \left[\left\{ 1 - \left(1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1+\theta} \right) e^{-\theta x_i} \right\} \right] \right\} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial b} \ln L &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial b} \left\{ n * \log \left\{ \frac{ab\theta^2}{B(l,m)(1+\theta)} \right\} - \theta \sum_{i=1}^n x_i + \sum_{i=1}^n \log(1+x_i) + \right. \\ &(l-1) \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\log \left[1 - \left\{ 1 - \left\{ 1 - \left(1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1+\theta} \right) e^{-\theta x_i} \right\}^a \right\}^b \right] \right] + (mb-1) \\ &\left. \sum_{i=1}^n \log \left[1 - \left\{ 1 - \left(1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1+\theta} \right) e^{-\theta x_i} \right\}^a \right] + (a-1) \sum_{i=1}^n \log \left[\left\{ 1 - \left(1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1+\theta} \right) e^{-\theta x_i} \right\} \right] \right\} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial l} \ln L &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial l} \{n * \log \left\{ \frac{ab\theta^2}{B(l, m)(1 + \theta)} \right\} - \theta \sum_{i=1}^n x_i + \sum_{i=1}^n \log(1 + x_i) + \\ (l - 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\log \left[1 - \{1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1 + \theta}) e^{-\theta x_i}\}^a\}^b \right] \right] + (mb - 1) \\ \sum_{i=1}^n \log[1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1 + \theta}) e^{-\theta x_i}\}^a] + (a - 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \log[\{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1 + \theta}) e^{-\theta x_i}\}] &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial m} \ln L &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial m} \{n * \log \left\{ \frac{ab\theta^2}{B(l, m)(1 + \theta)} \right\} - \theta \sum_{i=1}^n x_i + \sum_{i=1}^n \log(1 + x_i) + \\ (l - 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\log \left[1 - \{1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1 + \theta}) e^{-\theta x_i}\}^a\}^b \right] \right] + (mb - 1) \\ \sum_{i=1}^n \log[1 - \{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1 + \theta}) e^{-\theta x_i}\}^a] + (a - 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \log[\{1 - (1 + \frac{\theta x_i}{1 + \theta}) e^{-\theta x_i}\}] &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Since these equations are non-linear in nature, therefore, we cannot be solved analytically. Hence, some numerical techniques are used to solve them.

VIII. SIMULATION STUDY

The simulation study is performed to generate random variables from BKw-L (θ, a, b, l, m) distribution. The behavior of the Maximum Likelihood (ML) estimates are assessed using bias and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) measures. The algorithm of generating random numbers from the BKw-L distribution is mentioned below:

Step I:

Generate a random variable Y distributed as the one parameter Lindley distribution whose pdf is close to $f(x)$, the pdf of the BKw-L distribution.

Step II:

Generate $U \sim (0,1)$ (Independent of Y)

Step III:

If $U \leq \frac{f(Y)}{cg(Y)}$, then set $X = Y$; otherwise go back to step I.

The above steps are repeated until a sample of the desired size is reached.

Table 2 shows the ML estimate of the parameters, bias and RMSE for the generated samples of size 50,100,250,500 and 800 for two different set of values of the parameters.

Let the true value of the parameter a be a_0 and the MLE be \hat{a} . Then the Bias of \hat{a} in estimating a_0 and RMSE are given by

$$\text{Bias}(a) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{a} - a_0) \text{ and } \text{RMSE}(a) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{a} - a_0)^2}$$

The average values of Bias and RMSE have been calculated by considering 1000 replicates.

Table 2: ML estimates, Bias and RMSE of the parameters of BKw-L distribution for $a = 2; b = 0.8; l = 5; m = 3; \theta = 1$

Parameter		Sample Size				
		50	100	250	500	800
a	ML estimate	5.117	4.3334	3.299	2.7860	2.4332
	Bias	3.1147	2.9334	2.099	1.3860	0.4332
	RMSE	0.4750	0.4455	0.3471	0.2664	0.1204
b	ML estimate	1.4233	1.3038	0.9418	0.8569	0.5234
	Bias	0.9434	0.5038	0.2969	0.1418	0.0366
	RMSE	0.1494	0.1053	0.1012	0.0692	0.0554
l	ML estimate	4.5342	4.2949	4.1357	3.1478	3.0689
	Bias	0.8643	0.7949	0.4658	0.3522	0.0689
	RMSE	0.3621	0.2447	0.2301	0.1949	0.1803
m	ML estimate	4.8138	4.5634	3.7219	2.8121	2.5225
	Bias	2.7634	1.8138	0.7219	0.7121	0.4225
	RMSE	0.5840	0.4059	0.2771	0.2177	0.1475
θ	ML estimate	1.7767	1.4931	1.0246	0.7271	0.6592
	Bias	0.7931	0.7767	0.1271	0.0408	0.0246
	RMSE	0.1462	0.1140	0.0629	0.0289	0.0170

Table 2 clearly shows that the Bias and RMSE decrease when sample size increases. This points towards consistency of the ML estimates of the parameters of BKw-L distribution.

IX. APPLICATION

In this section, two real life data sets have been considered to exhibit the real-life application of the proposed distribution and to show its advantage over existing models, the competing models such as Beta Kumaraswamy exponential (BKw-E) distribution, Kumaraswamy-Lindley (Kw-L) distribution and Beta-Lindley (Beta-L) distribution have been considered. The first data set shows the annual maximum precipitation (inches) for one rain gauge in fort Collins, Colorado from 1900 through 1999 Katz.et al. [8]

and the second data set represents the lifetimes (in days) of 43 leukaemia patients by Bryson et al. [1]. Here, we consider the criteria viz., AIC, BIC, CAIC and HQIC whose formulae are given below:

$$AIC = 2k - 2\ln(L)$$

$$AICC = AIC + \frac{2k(k + 1)}{n - k - 1}$$

$$BIC = k\ln(n) - 2\ln(L)$$

$$HQIC = -2L + 2k\ln(\ln(n))$$

Where, k is the no. of parameters in the statistical model, n is the sample size and -2logL is the maximized value of the log likelihood function under the considered model.

Table 3 displays MLE of the parameters, AIC, BIC, CAIC and HQIC values for the data set I.

Table 3: MLE of the parameters, AIC, BIC, CAIC and HQIC values for the data set I

Model	ML estimates	AIC	BIC	CAIC	HQIC
BKw-L	$a = 22.37$ $b = 0.0631$ $l = 3.568$ $m = 1.002$ $\theta = 0.125$	1431.42	1444.446	1432.058	1436.692
BKw-E	$a = 0.0012$ $b = 0.0004$ $l = 2.509$ $m = 0.876$ $\theta = 0.008$	2076.35	2089.376	2076.988	2081.622
Kw-L	$a = 2.208e + 02$ $b = 1.95e + 05$ $\theta = 1.192e-02$	102049.2	102057	102049.4	102052.4
Beta-L	$a = 17.02$ $b = 1.19$ $\theta = 23.10$	482141	482148.8	482141.2	482144.2

Table 4 displays MLE of the parameters, AIC, BIC, CAIC and HQIC values for the data set II

Table 4: MLE of the parameters, AIC, BIC, CAIC and HQIC values for the data set II

Model	ML estimates	AIC	BIC	CAIC	HQIC
BKw-L	$a = 3.4139$ $b = 0.6735$ $l = 16.8896$ $m = 7.7219$ $\theta = 0.0034$	12131.25	12140.06	12132.87	12134.5
BKw-E	$a = 7.750$ $b = 5.680$ $l = 1.200$ $m = 8.50$ $\theta = 0.0097$	14738.7	14747.51	14740.32	14741.95
Kw-L	$a = 1.8500$ $b = 0.3840$ $\theta = 0.0156$	30618.39	30623.67	30619.01	30620.34
Beta-L	$a = 17.02$ $b = 0.2439$ $\theta = 24.24$	10116631	10116636	10116632	10116633

Since the least value of the above-mentioned criteria represents the best fitted distribution, so from table 3 and table 4 it is clear that the proposed model i.e., BKw-L distribution leads to a superior fit in comparison the considered competing probability models

X. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper, a characterization of Lindley distribution has been developed through Beta generated Kumaraswamy-G family of distributions viz., the beta generated Kumaraswamy Lindley distribution (BKw-L). The pdf and c.d.f of this distribution have been derived and different statistical properties such as mean, median, mode, skewness, kurtosis, behavior of the ratio and product of independently distributed BKw-L variates, reliability & hazard curves have been inspected. From the statistical properties, it has been observed that the behaviour of the BKw-L distribution depends partially on the parameter b and θ , i.e., greater value of b and θ may affect the structure of the proposed distribution. Also, the graphical plots and the probability distribution of the maximum or minimum order statistic have been derived from BKw-L distribution. For measuring inequality, the expressions of Bonferroni and Lorenz curve have been derived. Here, simulation has been done for assessing the performance of the maximum likelihood estimates of the parameters and the estimates have been found to be consistent. Finally, the two real life data sets have been considered to show the applicability of the proposed distribution and the goodness of fit results show the superiority of the proposed model in modelling positively skewed data sets in comparison to some existing models.

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